

Kinematic Intrinsic Null-Space Motor Control for Human Bodily Augmentation

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Abstract—Nowadays, the centrality of the sensorimotor skills in humans has been largely overshadowed by the augmentation of cognitive abilities granted by technologies as smartphones. Our idea focuses on the enhancement of human sensorimotor capabilities obtained by allowing humans to directly control robotic extra limbs as body extensions. The strategy capitalises on human body redundancy to concurrently control natural and artificial limbs. To this end, we introduce an innovative control strategy based on the exploitation of the kinematic null-space to control an extra degree of actuation.

I. INTRODUCTION

Assistive robots have been gradually proposed as technological aids for rehabilitation and functional substitution/augmentation [1], [2]. Wearable and grounded robotic extra limbs (arms and fingers) are representative examples of the technological and scientific achievements in this field [3], [4]. When adopted as technological supports for assistance and rehabilitation purposes, ease of use and ease of learning become crucial to foster device acceptance. Such ease should be recognizable under several aspects, ranging from the intuitiveness of the system control strategy to the user's autonomy while using the technology. Despite that, successful and intuitive strategies to cooperate and control the aforementioned aids are still not well established.

In this context, the goal of this research is to introduce a new control paradigm which is highly focused on users and their tasks. The underlying idea is to exploit the redundancy of the human kinematic chain to control additional degrees of actuation (DoAs). In this aim, we defined the *kinematic Intrinsic Null-Space* control paradigm and we applied it to control an extra DoA in a natural, comfortable, and intuitive way. To the best of our knowledge, this represents the first attempt to investigate the feasibility and usability of this novel control strategy for human-device interaction.

II. NULL-SPACE CONTROL FOR MOTOR AUGMENTATION

Motor augmentation consists in exploiting the musculoskeletal redundancies to directly control robotic extra-limbs that cooperate with the human to perform an augmented motor task. In this study, we focus on kinematic redundancy, i.e. body motions that do not affect the action of the natural limbs, a concept which is related to muscular redundancy [5]. An illustrative example of motor augmentation is depicted in Fig. 1,

Fig. 1: An impaired subject exploiting the kinematic intrinsic null-space of the arm involved in the task to control the robotic extra-limb, while simultaneously holding the glass.

where a subject with a paretic limb is using the unimpaired arm and a robotic arm to pour water. She exploits the kinematic null-space of the arm to control the robot. This use case can be considered as a paradigm of the motor augmentation theory: taking advantage of movements in the null-space lets the user control an extra DoA using those body parts already involved in the task, not to compromise the use of other limbs which can be involved in further parallel motor tasks.

To understand the potentiality of the proposed approach, one should consider the wide range of movements that can be performed to complete a given task. This redundancy is not surprising considering the complexity of the human body. Zatsiorsky in [6] estimated that there are 148 movable bones and 147 joints in the human body, which lead to 244 degrees of freedom (DoFs), a huge number compared with the DoFs required by some simple tasks. Despite this, many control interfaces for assistive devices take advantage of functional DoFs rather than redundant DoFs. A possible justification for this common design choice lies in the fact that we often are not fully aware of this redundancy. Indeed, we perform the movements related to a certain task on the basis of what feels more natural, without analysing all the possible kinematic configurations. Moreover, when developing human-device interfaces, engineers tend to search for standard design guidelines to match requirements of wide ranges of users. On the contrary, the distinction between functional and redundant degrees of freedom changes according to the user and the task.

Fig. 2: From data collection to workspace clustering in a representative trial. In (a), the trajectory depicted by the central point of the user’s right hand back. In (b) the identified clusters, whereas in (c) the considered data for the PCA computation.

Thus only an accurate *a-priori* evaluation of the user-task pair (e.g., user’s motor features) can provide parameters to properly calibrate a control interface based on the kinematic redundancy.

III. KINEMATIC INTRINSIC NULL-SPACE CONTROL

A. Definition

Considering the kinematic space of the whole human body, the kinematic null-space is defined by the set of joint velocities that do not produce any hand (or foot) velocity in the given configuration of the natural limb. Once the task to be accomplished is identified, we distinguish between:

- i) kinematic Extrinsic Null-Space (ENS);
- ii) kinematic Intrinsic Null-Space (INS).

The kinematic null-space of joints which are not involved in such a task belongs to the first category, whereas the INS refers only to joints directly employed in the task. For instance, grabbing a box with two hands directly involves joints of shoulders, upper arms, forearms, and wrists, which are all considered for the INS computation. The kinematic null-space of all the other joints (e.g., knees and ankles) is the ENS.

B. Identification

Agas, habits, and lifestyle strongly influence the way people interact with objects and surroundings. Thus, there is not a strict mathematical definition of INS, since each individual is prone to perform tasks differently. To overcome this problem, we developed a procedure to identify the kinematic intrinsic null-space focusing on the case of a single-arm task. Even if the proposed methodology can be used for controlling an arbitrary number of DoAs, we tested the effectiveness for one DoA only.

To record arm joint angle values, 39 retro-reflective markers are attached to the subject in accordance with the Oxford Full Body Model [7], who is located at the centre of a room equipped with ten Vicon Bonita cameras. The body posture is reconstructed online by means of Vicon Nexus 3.10 Software (Vicon Motion Systems Ltd, UK). A static acquisition and anthropometric measurements are used to create and calibrate each user’s skeleton model. Then, to compute the null-space of a single arm, the user is asked to move the arm freely in ten different hand positions, namely ‘starting null-space points’, while movements are recorded and analysed to detect

joint velocity vectors whose contribution to the hand motion is negligible. These points are chosen at the boundaries of the user’s workspace, which is in turn a subspace of the reachable peripersonal space. For each starting null-space point, joint values belonging to the null-space are transformed through Principal Component Analysis (PCA) into a set of values of linearly uncorrelated variables, called principal components (PCs). Depending on if the percentage of data variation explained by the first PC is at least 80% or not, either the first one or the norm of the first two PCs are taken as directions for controlling the extra DoA. Thus, the multidimensional INS is transformed into the input for controlling an extra DoA. Steps from data collection to workspace clustering in a representative trial are reported in Fig. 2.

C. Online Estimation

Since the INS depends on the position of the hand (i.e., the current body posture), the ten first PCs evaluated in the previous step are used to create an interpolation grid for estimating the null-space in the entire workspace. A Delaunay triangulation-based natural neighbour interpolation is used to reconstruct the null-space [8].

A dedicated computer acquires data from the tracking system, automatically reconstructs the user’s skeleton, and fits the kinematic model. Thus, joint values and body segment positions are streamed in real time. A middleware is in charge of computing the projection of the joint values to the actual principal component, which is evaluated by interpolating the principal components computed in the identification phase depending on the current hand position. The resulting value is used to control the additional degree of actuation required by the task.

IV. EXPERIMENTAL VALIDATION

To validate the proposed control strategy, the experimental campaign was aimed at answering the following questions:

- *Is the proposed strategy exploitable for controlling an extra robotic device?*
- *Is the motion correspondent to the first principal component easy to learn?*

A two-step validation procedure was carried out. In the first phase we validated the proposed framework in a virtual

Fig. 3: The user wearing retro-reflective markers is in a). In b) the virtual scene. The user moves and orients the red ellipsoid, while the white ones are the goals.

environment, then we moved to the real one. This choice allowed us to conduct a deeper and more precise analysis.

Virtual Environment: A virtual environment was generated through an *ad-hoc* C# software (developed with Unity) and rendered using an Oculus Rift DK2 [9]. Participants to the experiments were tasked to seat and to match virtual ellipsoids moving the arm. Nine goals were positioned in the reachable peripersonal space and displayed one at a time (see Fig. 3). The user was able to control both position and orientation in the space of an additional ellipsoid. The coordinates of the center of the ellipsoid corresponded to the coordinates of the user’s right palm (left if the subject was left-handed), while the ellipsoid rotation was controlled through the kinematic intrinsic null-space. Taking advantage of the developed software, time to accomplish the task, position error, and orientation error were logged and a-posteriori analysed.

Real Environment: In this phase, participants to the experiments were tasked to use the proposed control strategy for pouring a glass of water using a robotic arm (similarly to [10]). Also in this case, the user has to accomplish two tasks simultaneously, i.e. place the glass under the bottle, and at the same time, precisely control the robot (see Fig. 4). The aim of the experiment was to pour 30 g of water, and the deviation from the desired quantity was used as evaluation metric.

V. CONCLUSIONS AND FUTURE WORK

This study presented a novel approach for controlling extra DoAs exploiting the redundancy of the human body. This kind of control takes advantage of movements in the kinematic Intrinsic Null-Space to enable the user to easily and comfortably control assistive robots.

Firstly, we tested the proposed methodology in a virtual environment, proving its reliability and verifying it does not affect the performance of the primary task. Then, we used the control method in the real environment, assessing that it is easy to learn and easy to use in tasks of activities of daily living. Results of the experimental evaluation, supported by users’ feedback and opinions, revealed that the proposed

Fig. 4: The user holding a glass and pouring the water using a robotic arm controlled through the kinematic intrinsic null-space.

control strategy is suitable for controlling an extra DoA in the envisaged scenarios.

Future research directions include expanding this INS-based control strategy for a larger number of degrees of actuation.

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